

Genetic and Environmental Aspects of Abnormal Calving in Haryana Cattle

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Abstract The present investigation was conducted to examine the specific incidence of calving abnormalities such as abortion, dystocia, premature birth and still birth in relation to various genetic and environmental factors in Haryana cattle at the Govt. livestock farm, Hastinapur in Northern India. The analyst carried out on data of 641 calving records of 193 adult cows divided up to the tenth Lactation into four seasons which were born for eighteen years of period. The overall abnormal calving was 5.1% in the herd and was significantly ($P < 0.05$) affected by season and period of birth. Higher abnormal calving were found during Summer. No specific trend in abnormal calving was seen in parity and period of calving. The heritability estimates for abnormal parturitions was found to be very low (0.08) indicated that this trait is mostly governed by the environmental factors. The repeatability a concept derived from quantitative genetics theory is a statistics that describe the degree to which variation within individuals contributes to total variation in a population. It was very low (0.11) for abnormal birth. It varies from population to population and environment to environment.

Keywords Genetic and Non-genetic Factors, Heritability, Repeatability, Haryana Cattle.

Introduction Haryana breed of cow, an important dual purpose breed of zebu cattle endowed with adaptability to perform well under harsh, sub tropical climatic condition. Calving abnormalities affect the herd life, reproductive efficiency of cows and economy of dairy herds and are responsible for culling of the cows. It has been observed that indigenous breeds are less susceptible for the calving abnormalities as compare to cross breeds Cows. Information on incidence and inheritance of calving abnormalities in dairy cattle in advanced temperate countries is well reported. Identification of genetic and non-genetic factors influencing calving abnormalities will facilitate developing breeding and management strategies for realizing higher intensity and increased accuracy of selection of elite cows in the herd. Premature disposal of female calves before reaching mulch herd and undesirable disposal of lactating cows are the major constraints in achieving larger herd size. Therefore, the present study was undertaken with the influence of genetic and non-genetic factors as influence the calving abnormalities.

Aim of study

The objective of this paper is to study the Genetic and Environmental Aspects of Abnormal Calving in Haryana Cattle.

Review of Literature

The literature review has been discussed in result and discussion section.

Methodology

The data for the present investigation were collected during the period of 1992 to 2009 from the records of Haryana cattle maintained at Govt. Livestock farm, Hastinapur in the Northern India. Data of 641 calving records of 193 adult cows were used to analyze the genetic and non-genetic influence on calving abnormalities. and disposal pattern of adult cows. The date was classified into two genetic parameters viz heritability and repeatability and non-genetic factors such as two parities groups, four periods and four seasons.

Analysis

The influence of non-genetic factors on incidence of calving abnormalities were analyzed by using analysis of variance (F-test). The sums of square calculated by the procedure outlined by Tomar (1998) as:

Total sum of squares = pqn

Group sum of squares = pqn - piqini

Error sum of squares=TSS - sum of the SS of all the effects

where, pi = ai/ni= average incidence in ith level of the effect.

qi = 1-pi

p = ai/ni is the average incidence in the whole population.

n = ni = Total number of cows in the population.

The following mathematical model was used to conduct the analysis of variance.

$Y_{ijkl} = \mu + Li + Pj + Sk + e_{ijkl}$

where, μ =overall mean

Li = effect of ith lactation (i = 1.....5)

Pj = effect of ith period (J=1.....4)

Sk = effect of kth Season (K=1..... 4)

e_{ijkl} = random error specific in the particular observation.

The genetic parameter as heritability based on first lactation data used by paternal half-sib correlation method.

as:

$y_{ij} = \mu + S_i + e_{ij}$

where, y_{ij} = record of the ith daughter of ith sire

μ = over all mean.

S_i = effect ith sire

e_{ij}= random error

The genetic parameter repeatability was estimated as:,

$t = (X-Y)/100$

where,

X= the percentage of cows susceptible in second lactation which were also susceptible in the first lactation.

Y= the percentage of cows susceptible in second lactation which were resistant in the first lactation.

Result and Discussion

The data presented in Table 1. On the incidence of abnormal births have shown that the overall incidence was 5.1 percent in this herd. Almost similar incidence of abnormal birth varying from 4.4 to 4.9 percent have been reported by Bhattacharya and Buchoo (2008), while a little higher value 5.75 percent for the trait was estimated by upadhaya etal. (2014) in sahiwal cows, and 5.4%. by Mukherjee and Tomar (2000) in crossbreds cows.

The incidence of abnormal Calvings varied from 2.6 to 6.7 percent among the cows of different lactations (Table 1) and the incidence was higher in first calvers then older ones. This may be because of genital organs of first calf heifers are not well accustomed to the normal act of parturition. In the analysis of variance it was found. that parity order was not significant on abnormal calving. This supported the findings of Abbas (2005), Benik and Nasker (2006) and upadhaya (2014)

Table: 1 Incidence of abnormal births (%) and sex ratio (%males) in relation to different non genetic factors.

Effect	Total Births	Abnormal births		Male births		Female births	Total Normal Births
		No	%	No	%(sex ratio)		
Lact-1	193	13	6.7	83	46.1	97	180
2	153	6	3.9	74	50.3	73	147
3	116	3	2.6	50	44.2	63	113
4	77	5	6.5	31	43.0	41	72
5	102	6	5.8	47	48.9	49	96
Period							
1	74	5	6.7	29	42.0	40	69
2	167	3	1.8	79	48.2	85	164
3	226	9	3.9	102	47.0	115	217
4	174	6	9.2	75	47.5	83	158
Season							
Winter	298	13	4.3	143	50.2	142	285
Summer	135	12	8.8	50	40.6	73	123
Rainy	139	5	3.6	62	46.2	72	134
Autumn	69	3	4.3	30	45.4	36	66
Overall	641	33	5.1	285	46.8	323	608

Table:2 ANOVA showing the effect of different non-genetic factors on abnormal births and sex ratio. (M.S Values).

Sources of variation	Degree of Freedom	Abnormal calving	Sex ratio
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Lactations	4	0.0629	0.1149
Periods	3	0.1741*	0.0652
Seasons	3	0.1669*	0.5177**
Error		0.0482(630)	0.2019(597)

*P<0.05

The period of calving was found to influence the incidence of abnormal birth varied from 1.8 to 9.2 percent among the cows calved in different periods (Table 1 and 2). This may be due to the variation in environmental factors over the periods. Similar findings were also reported by Abbas (2005), Banik and Naskar (2006), Shahi and Kumar (2006), Singh et al. (2011), Ghosu et al. (2013) and Upadhaya et al. (2013) in Indian breeds of cows.

The rate of abnormal calving was found to be highest among summer calves (8.8%) while, it was Lowest (3.6%) during rainy season (Table 1) statistically the differences among seasons were found significant (Table 2) similar finding was also reported by Wakchaure et al (2021) in crossbred cows. On the contrary Benik and Naskar (2006) and Sahi and Kumar (2006) have reported that season had no effect on the rate or abnormal calving.

Genetic Parameters

Heritability and Repeatability estimation-

The heritability estimates for abnormal parturition was found to be very Low (0.08) (Table 3). It Indicate that this trait is mostly governed by the environmental factors, Abnormal calving was being affected with summer season in the study. Therefore care should be taken during summer season regarding given fodder and shade to the cows. Low heritability of abnormal births had also been reported by Sing et al (2002), Benik(2005) and Atrey et al. (2005).

The result presented in table 3, for repeatability estimates for different disorders in this herd of Haryana Cattle have shown that the abnormal births had low repeatability (0.11). It was thus not possible to predict the type of calving in future gestation. based on the type of calving in previous gestation. This supported result reported by Mukherjee and Tomar (2000).

Conclusion The incidence of calving abnormalities in cows 5.1 percent, It was varied from 2.6 to 6.7 percent among the calves of different lactations, and the incidence was higher in first calvers then older ones. The non-genetic effect, parity had no significant influence on calving incidence while, period and season of birth showed significant effects on such incidence. Genetic parameters such as heritability and repeatability was very low as 0.08 and 0.11 respectively in the calving abnormality. The present investigation revealed that the incidence of these abnormalities can be reduce only through better management rather than through genetic manipulation.

Table:3 Heritability and repeatability of different lactation disorders.

Lactation Disorders	Heritability	Repeatability
Abnormal births	0.08	0.11
Prolapse	0.27	0.31
Retention of placenta	0.18	0.20
Metritis	0.20	0.21
Mastitis	0.16	0.17
Blood in milk	0.10	0.12
Repeat breeding	0.08	0.11
Anoestrus	0.09	0.10

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